

Side-looking endoscopic micro-optics: comparison between state-of-the-art two-photon polymerization printing techniques

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Abstract: Over the past few decades, additive manufacturing has emerged as the third pillar of fabrication, besides formative and subtractive manufacturing. 3D printing unlocks new possibilities across various fields, including communication, electronics, and medical applications. By using two-photon polymerization (2PP), micro-optical components and devices, such as endoscopes, can be manufactured with the highest precision. Here, we compare 2PP and two-photon grayscale lithography (2GL) printing of side-looking optical coherence tomography (OCT) endoscopes. We utilize two commercial 3D printers, the Photonic Professional GT (PPGT) and Quantum X (both Nanoscribe GmbH & Co. KG, Germany). We present the microscopic appearance, quantify topography deviations, and analyze optical performance through beam profile measurements. Both printing quality and speed are compared across state-of-the-art machines, as well as between two different printing modes, 2PP and 2GL.

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1. Introduction

For about one decade, 2PP 3D printing has been a fundamental fabrication method for producing high-performance optical elements with minimal sizes and sub-micrometer accuracy [1–23]. Micro-optical components are used in a wide range of fields, including quantum technology [24–26], communication and display technology [27,28], holography [29–31], and biomedical optics [32–36]. Especially in the field of endoscopy [5,37–41], 3D-printed optical coherence tomography (OCT) [42–44] devices hold great promise for significant advancements, such as improved imaging quality and miniaturization. Their high optical performance at extremely small dimensions enables minimally invasive endoscopic procedures, reducing patient harm. Additionally, this technology allows for the visualization of previously inaccessible areas, marking a major leap forward in diagnostics and treatment.

With 3D printing now an established fabrication method for micro-optics, today's challenges regard improving imaging quality while reducing fabrication time, making it a viable manufacturing technique in research and also in medical industry. In this study, we compare the capabilities of two-photon polymerization (2PP) and two-photon grayscale lithography (2GL) printing [45,46], as well as two different 3D printers: Quantum X (QX) and Photonics Professional GT (PPGT) (both Nanoscribe GmbH & Co. KG, Germany). We analyze the appearance under an optical microscope, quantify topography deviations using confocal microscopy, and examine

beam profiles. By gaining both qualitative and quantitative insights into current standards and limitations, we aim to pave the way for future advancements across various fields of application.

2. Fabrication

The 3D printed optical elements are fabricated directly onto a fiber tip. In Fig. 1, we present a schematic of the endoscope, as well as its fabrication scheme.

Fig. 1. Total internal reflectance (TIR) endoscope design schematic. (a) Light propagation through the endoscope. The light is transmitted into a no-core-fiber piece of length 450 μm. At the TIR surface, the light is reflected at a right angle and leaves the endoscope through the distal surface. The designed wavelength is 658 nm. (b) Printing process onto the fiber. A 63x objective with a NA of 1.4 is used together with IP-S photoresist. A schematic drawing of the two printing modes (2PP and 2GL) is shown. (c) Microscopic image (VHX600, Keyence Deutschland GMBH) of an endoscope printed by the PPGT. (d) SEM Image (SEM Gemini 560, ZEISS) of the same endoscope.

The endoscope consists of three fundamental components, a single mode fiber (Thorlabs SM600), a no-core piece, and the 3D printed TIR component. The light is guided through the fiber, which has a cladding diameter of 125 μm . The no-core piece with similar diameter and a length of 450 μm is spliced onto the fiber. This allows the light to expand within the no-core piece. First, the light strikes the total internal reflectance (TIR) surface, reflecting the light by 90° , enabling the side-looking ability. The light subsequently exits through the distal surface and is focused to a diffraction limited spot at a distance of 500 μm . The TIR component is 3D printed directly onto the spliced no-core fiber segment. Therefore, optimizing the 3D printing process is essential to ensure high-quality endoscopic imaging.

In this study, two 3D printers are used, Quantum X and Photonics Professional GT (PPGT) (both Nanoscribe GmbH, Germany). The printing process relies on two-photon absorption to polymerize a photoresist (Nanoscribe IP-S) within a small volume around the focus known as the voxel. This technique allows for the creation of arbitrary free-form geometries. Both printers use a femtosecond-pulsed laser with a wavelength of 780 nm. The laser is focused by a 63x magnification, 1.4 numerical aperture (NA) objective (Carl Zeiss Microscopy GmbH, Jena, Deutschland). Two galvanometric mirrors scan the laser in x- and y-direction, a process known as hatching. To achieve movement along the z-axis, a piezoelectric stage is employed to precisely position the sample—in this case, the fiber—a technique referred to as slicing. Figure 1(b) illustrates the layer-by-layer printing process on the fiber tip. The zoom-in depicts a schematic of the two printing modes. In contrast to common 2PP printing, in the 2GL mode the size of the voxel is varied by dynamically changing the power during fabrication, so that curved surfaces are printed without the creation of large steps between the printed layers [46]. In our work, this surface smoothing effect will be analyzed for the TIR surface depicted in Fig. 1(a).

We use NanoPrintX and DescribeX as the printing software for Quantum X and PPGT systems, respectively. For each manufacturing type (PPGT 2PP, QX 2PP, and QX 2GL) a different set of printing parameters is used as displayed in Table 1. For the PPGT these settings result in an approximate printing time of three hours. Figure 1(c), (d) present microscopic appearance and an SEM image of the endoscope printed by the PPGT, respectively. For the QX 2PP mode the total printing time is approximately one hour. For the Quantum X 2GL mode the printing time is reduced to just 15 minutes, since the slicing distance is increased to 0.4 μm . In addition to the four printing parameters listed in Table 1, the 2GL mode offers some more advanced settings, which need optimization to further improve the printing quality.

Table 1. Printing parameters for the three different manufacturing types. Slicing distance, hatching distance, laser power, and laser scan speed are adjusted for each printing type. For the QX 2GL mode three additional parameters are used. The number of outer layers printed in 2GL mode is set to 4, the minimal power used when varying the voxel size is set to 9 mW, and the power exponent is set to 0.95. The repetition rate is 80 MHz and the pulse duration is between 100 and 150 fs

Printing Parameter	PPGT 2PP	QX 2PP	QX 2GL
Slicing distance [μm]	0.1	0.1	0.4
Hatching distance [μm]	0.1	0.1	0.1
Laser power [mW]	24	45	70
Laser scan speed [mm s^{-1}]	25	40	40

In 2GL mode, we set the number of outer layers printed in 2GL mode to 4, the minimal power used when varying the voxel size to 9 mW, and the power exponent to 0.95. These values were determined by analyzing the surfaces of several fabricated endoscopes with confocal microscopy (Nanofocus μSurf Expert, NanoFocus AG, Germany). After printing, the liquid photoresist is

removed by immersion into mr-Dev 600 (Micro Resist Technology) for 12 minutes, followed by a rinse in isopropyl alcohol for 3 minutes.

3. Visual analysis

We inspect both the TIR surfaces and the distal surfaces with an optical microscope (Keyence VHX 6000, Keyence Corp., Osaka, Japan, no focus stacking). Figure 2 compares the TIR surfaces of the three fabrication types, being PPGT 2PP, Quantum X 2PP and Quantum X 2GL. In Fig. 2(a) we see the TIR surface of the PPGT 2PP print, which depicts vertical stripes stemming from the slicing steps during the printing process. Figure 2(b),(c) display the TIR surfaces printed by the Quantum X. Here, we do not see dominant vertical stripes. Instead, we can identify a grid of horizontal and vertical lines of equal height. Figure 2(d)-(f) present the TIR surfaces of the three manufacturing types with laser illumination through the endoscopes. We incouple a laser with a wavelength of 658 nm and inspect the light scattering through the TIR surface. In theory, the TIR surface should reflect 100% of incoming light. However, because of printing imperfections, light will scatter through the TIR surface, linking the printing quality to the amount of scattered light. Figure 2(d) indicates that the light is scattered both at the edges and through the center of the TIR surface. Figure 2(e),(f) prove that in the case of both Quantum X prints, less light is leaked through the center of the TIR surface. Here, we see the highest light intensity at the top of the TIR surfaces (right edge in the microscope images). This indicates that the light is reflected properly at the TIR surface and subsequently is transmitted through the distal surface, where we then observe high light intensity.

Fig. 2. Optical microscope images of the TIR surfaces comparing the different fabrication schemes with and without laser illumination through the endoscope. (a-c) TIR surfaces without laser illumination comparing manufacturing with PPGT 2PP, Quantum X 2PP, and Quantum X 2GL. (d-f) TIR surfaces with laser illumination through the endoscopes comparing the light transmission through the TIR surfaces of the different manufacturing types. The white scale bar has a length of 25 μm .

Figure 3 presents the corresponding distal surfaces for each type of endoscope. In Fig. 3(a) we observe vertical stripes on the distal surface of the PPGT print. Again, this contrasts with the smooth surface we see in Fig. 3(b),(c) when inspecting the Quantum X prints. Figure 2 and Fig. 3 display corresponding differences between the endoscopes printed by the PPGT and the

Quantum X. In Fig. 3(d)-(f) we see the laser illumination transmitted through the distal surfaces of the respective endoscope types. In Fig. 3(f), we observe a decreased light intensity compared to Fig. 3(d),(e) due to the input laser power being lower. In Fig.3(d) we can see distortion due to the vertical stripes in the transmitted light. In comparison, we observe that light in Fig. 3(e),(f) is less disturbed.

Fig. 3. Optical microscope images of the distal surfaces comparing the different fabrication schemes with and without laser illumination through the endoscope. (d-f) A laser is coupled into the endoscopes. The white scale bar depicts a length of 25 μm . (a), (d) The PPGT print shows vertical stripes again. In comparison, the surfaces printed by the Quantum X (b), (c), (e), (f) are smoother. Hence, the transmitted light is disturbed less. The difference between Quantum X 2PP printing (b), (e) and Quantum X 2GL printing (c), (f) is negligible.

With these results, we can draw a set of conclusions about the performance of the different types of manufacturing. In Fig. 2(a) and Fig. 3(a) we observe vertical stripes on the surfaces of the endoscope printed with the PPGT. This is caused by the slicing steps and potential xy-offsets during the layer-by-layer printing process. The Quantum X technology fabricates smoother surfaces by having a smaller offset between printed layers and, in case of the 2GL mode, by varying the voxel size according to the curved shape, when printing the TIR surface. Furthermore, from Fig. 2(d)-(f), we conclude that a higher roughness on the TIR surface, characterized by vertical stripes, leads to increased light transmittance through the center of the TIR surface. As the purpose of the TIR surface is to reflect the light as efficiently as possible, we can draw a direct link between the printing quality of the endoscopes and their optical performance. We observe increased light transmission through a damaged spot in Fig. 2(f) confirming this behavior. In addition, the transmission of light through the distal surface appears disturbed by the increased surface roughness of the endoscope printed by the PPGT in Fig. 3(d). On the other hand, we find that the surfaces printed with the Quantum X in 2PP and 2GL modes appear much alike. Here, 2GL printing does not further improve the surface quality by reducing its roughness, as expected. However, it is important to note that the 2GL mode prints with slicing steps four times higher than the 2PP mode. Although further reduction of the 2GL slicing step size would not lead to a significant decrease in roughness, it is a clear advantage being able to print four times faster in 2GL mode compared to 2PP mode while maintaining equal surface quality.

4. Topography analysis

To analyze the surfaces more quantitatively, we measure their topography with a confocal microscope (μ surf expert, NanoFocus AG, Germany). This way, we gain insight about the surface shape deviations and roughness values.

Figure 4 plots the measurements made on the TIR surfaces of the three types of endoscope.

Fig. 4. Topography and roughness comparison of the TIR surfaces of the three manufacturing schemes. (a)-(c) TIR surface topography measured via confocal microscopy. (d)-(f) Extracted TIR surface roughness by further analysis of the confocal microscopy data. The columns represent the three manufacturing modes.

Fig. 4(a)-(c) present the topography of the TIR surface. The free-form shape designed for the TIR surface becomes visible, having a height of around $4\ \mu\text{m}$ at the apex. Figure 4(d)-(f) depict the high spatial frequencies of the confocal data; they represent what we term surface roughness. We extract surface roughness from the topographic analysis by applying a Gaussian filter with a spatial cutoff frequency of $\frac{1}{8\ \mu\text{m}}$. The height ranges around $\pm 100\ \text{nm}$ peak-to-valley. We see a similar surface quality of both QX prints, while the PPGT print is distinctly rougher. We determine a root-mean-square (rms) roughness (Sq) for the three samples in Fig. 4(d)-(f). The PPGT has the highest roughness value with $Sq = 17.5\ \text{nm}$, followed by the QX 2GL print with $Sq = 13.3\ \text{nm}$ and the QX 2PP print with $Sq = 8.8\ \text{nm}$. The topographic analysis supports the results of the optical microscope. The PPGT print is significantly rougher than the QX prints.

Figure 5 presents the topographical analysis of the distal surfaces. Unlike the TIR surface, the distal surface is designed flat. The samples in Fig. 5(a), (b), and (c) depict a height of around $500\ \text{nm}$. This is partly due to the influence of the roughness on the height, but also due to imperfections when printing, e.g., the shrinkage of the polymerized photoresist or slight xy-drifts during the slicing process. When comparing Fig. 5(b), and (c), we see that the 2GL mode shows higher shape accuracy than the 2PP mode, despite the usage of a larger slicing distance. Figure 5(d), (e), and (f) present the roughness analysis of the distal surfaces. The PPGT print appearance in Fig. 5(d) is dominated by the vertical stripes, namely the slicing lines. This results in an rms roughness of $Sq = 17\ \text{nm}$, comparable to the Sq value of the TIR surface printed by the PPGT. Both Quantum X prints depict a similar surface roughness. Slicing and hatching lines can be seen to a similar extent. This is possible since the slicing lines are less dominant in those cases, and hence the hatching contour becomes visible. The rms roughness values of $Sq = 2.64\ \text{nm}$ for the Quantum X 2PP endoscope and $Sq = 1.93\ \text{nm}$ for the Quantum X 2GL endoscope reflect this observation, respectively. The roughness values of the QX distal surfaces are significantly lower

than the roughness value of the PPGT distal surface, which speaks for a more precise stage and laser adjustment in the Quantum X compared to the PPGT.

Fig. 5. Topography and roughness comparison of the distal surfaces of the three types of endoscopes. (a)-(c) distal surface topography measured via confocal microscopy (μ surf expert, NanoFocus AG, Germany). (d)-(f) Extracted distal surface roughness by further analysis of the confocal microscopy data. The columns represent the three manufacturing modes.

5. Beam profile analysis

Although optical performance greatly depends on the surface properties of the components, the fiber splice and alignment can disturb performance, which is why we directly characterize beam quality. We analyze the optical performance of the endoscopes by performing beam profile measurements, where we investigate both the axial and the radial intensity distributions. We utilize a setup previously described in [47]. We image the intensity distribution with a 60x magnification, 0.7 NA objective. We manually move the fiber along the z direction using a microscopic translation stage in steps of $10\ \mu\text{m}$. A total range of $1200\ \mu\text{m}$ is covered, while the designed focal length of the endoscope is $500\ \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 6 illustrates the beam profiles along the optical axis for all three types of endoscopes. The intensity distribution along the optical axis is color-plotted with cross sections in the x - and y -directions. In Fig. 6, we observe a slight discrepancy with respect to the designed and measured working distance of the three endoscopes. For QX prints, we see the highest intensity at around $z = 550$ to $600\ \mu\text{m}$. For the PPGT print, we observe the highest intensity around $z = 400$ to $450\ \mu\text{m}$.

All plots include graphs of the measured intensity distribution along the three axis centred at the focus and Gaussian fit curves, respectively. We additionally calculate the radial and axial full width-half maximum (FWHM) values in the x -/ and y -directions.

Table 2 compares the fitted FWHM values for the three types of endoscopes in the radial and axial directions. We can not see a decisive difference in performance between the endoscopes. The PPGT print exhibits the lowest FWHM value in the radial x -direction but is highly astigmatic.

Fig. 6. Beam profile analysis of the three endoscopes. (a)–(c) xz-view and (d)–(f) yz-view on the beam profile measured along the optical axis in steps of $10\ \mu\text{m}$. The radial and axial intensity distributions are plotted in white for each profile together with a Gaussian fit curve (orange-dotted). The wavelength is $658\ \text{nm}$.

The QX 2PP print is least astigmatic and also shows the lowest FWHM values on average. Here, it is important to note that the QX endoscopes show smoother intensity distributions compared to the endoscopes printed by the PPGT. Hence, the Gaussian fit curve aligns better with the actual data for the QX prints than for the PPGT print. This influences the returned fit values, e.g. the FWHM value.

Table 2. FWHM values for the three different endoscopes measured in radial and axial directions, each in x and y

Endoscope	Radial (x) [μm]	Radial (y) [μm]	Axial (x) [μm]	Axial (y) [μm]
PPGT	4.0	8.6	260	200
QX 2PP	5.3	4.7	190	200
QX 2GL	6.9	4.8	240	240

Qualitatively, QX-printed endoscopes show a smoother intensity distribution and less astigmatism. Quantitatively, this is roughly supported by the FWHM-data. We can not clearly connect the lower surface roughness of the QX prints with higher optical performance. This might indicate that for such particular micro-optical components, the shape accuracy of the overall structure is of higher importance than the surface roughness.

6. Conclusion

We investigated side-looking endoscopes printed by two different printing machines, the QX and the PPGT, and two different printing modes, 2PP and 2GL. The fabrication with the PPGT took about three hours; this time was reduced to 15 minutes when printing in 2GL mode on the Quantum X. This enables drastically faster research procedures, e.g., printing-parameter sweeps, and could have a significant impact for future industrial production.

Furthermore, the optical and confocal microscope images yielded a similar quality when produced with the two different QX printing modes, 2PP and 2GL. In comparison, the PPGT print exhibited Sq values up to five times higher, 17 nm compared to 3 nm than the QX prints. This aligns with the observations under the optical microscope, where the PPGT-printed endoscopes showed significantly larger slicing artifacts.

The beam profile analysis did not yield significant differences with regard to the calculated FWHM values for each endoscope. Still, the beam profile of the QX prints appeared smoother and with less astigmatism than the PPGT print.

In summary, a clear difference in surface quality was observed between the two printing machines. Although the 2GL printing mode was unable to further improve the surface quality or optical performance of the side-looking endoscope, it enabled printing speeds that far exceeded the speed of the 2PP printing modes, while maintaining similar performance.

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Data availability. Data underlying the results presented in this paper are not publicly available at this time but may be obtained from the authors upon reasonable request.

References

1. T. Gissibl, S. Thiele, A. Herkommer, *et al.*, “Two-photon direct laser writing of ultracompact multi-lens objectives,” *Nat. Photonics* **10**(8), 554–560 (2016).
2. T. Gissibl, S. Thiele, A. Herkommer, *et al.*, “Sub-micrometre accurate free-form optics by three-dimensional printing on single-mode fibres,” *Nat. Commun.* **7**(1), 11763 (2016).
3. T. Gissibl, M. Schmid, and H. Giessen, “Spatial beam intensity shaping using phase masks on single-mode optical fibers fabricated by femtosecond direct laser writing,” *Optica* **3**(4), 448 (2016).
4. S. Thiele, K. Arzenbacher, T. Gissibl, *et al.*, “3d-printed eagle eye: Compound microlens system for foveated imaging,” *Sci. Adv.* **3**(2), e1602655 (2017).
5. J. Li, S. Thiele, B. C. Quirk, *et al.*, “Ultrathin monolithic 3d printed optical coherence tomography endoscopy for preclinical and clinical use,” *Light: Sci. Appl.* **9**(1), 124 (2020).
6. C. Imiolczyk, T. K. Pfau, S. Thiele, *et al.*, “Ultracompact wavefront characterization of femtosecond 3d printed microlenses using double-frequency ronchi interferometry,” *Opt. Express* **32**(6), 9777 (2024).
7. M. Rumi and J. W. Perry, “Two-photon absorption: an overview of measurements and principles,” *Adv. Opt. Photonics* **2**(4), 451 (2010).
8. A.-I. Bunea, N. del Castillo Iniesta, A. Droumpali, *et al.*, “Micro 3d printing by two-photon polymerization: Configurations and parameters for the nanoscribe system,” *Micro* **1**(2), 164–180 (2021).
9. P. Somers, A. Münchinger, S. Maruo, *et al.*, “The physics of 3d printing with light,” *Nat. Rev. Phys.* **6**(2), 99–113 (2023).
10. D. Gonzalez-Hernandez, S. Varapnickas, A. Bertocini, *et al.*, “Micro-optics 3d printed via multi-photon laser lithography,” *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **11**(1), 2201701 (2023).
11. M. Kavalzhiev, J. E. Perez, Y. Ivanov, *et al.*, “Biocompatible 3d printed magnetic micro needles,” *Biomed. Phys. Eng. Express* **3**(2), 025005 (2017).
12. M. Thiel, J. Fischer, G. Von Freymann, *et al.*, “Direct laser writing of three-dimensional submicron structures using a continuous-wave laser at 532 nm,” *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **97**(22), 221102 (2010).
13. V. Hahn, P. Kiefer, T. Frenzel, *et al.*, “Rapid assembly of small materials building blocks (voxels) into large functional 3d metamaterials,” *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **30**(26), 1907795 (2020).
14. E. Skliutas, G. Merkininkaitė, S. Maruo, *et al.*, “Multiphoton 3d lithography,” *Nat. Rev. Methods Primers* **5**(1), 15 (2025).
15. S. Ristok, S. Thiele, A. Toulouse, *et al.*, “Stitching-free 3d printing of millimeter-sized highly transparent spherical and aspherical optical components,” *Opt. Mater. Express* **10**(10), 2370 (2020).
16. F. Kotz, A. S. Quick, P. Risch, *et al.*, “Two-photon polymerization of nanocomposites for the fabrication of transparent fused silica glass microstructures,” *Adv. Mater.* **33**(9), 2006341 (2021).

17. Y.-L. Zhang, Q.-D. Chen, H. Xia, *et al.*, “Designable 3d nanofabrication by femtosecond laser direct writing,” *Nano Today* **5**(5), 435–448 (2010).
18. J. Weinacker, S. Kalt, P. Kiefer, *et al.*, “On iterative pre-compensation of 3d laser-printed micro-optical components using confocal-optical microscopy,” *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **34**(12), 2309356 (2024).
19. D. Gonzalez-Hernandez, B. Sanchez-Padilla, D. Gailevičius, *et al.*, “Single-step 3d printing of micro-optics with adjustable refractive index by ultrafast laser nanolithography,” *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **11**(14), 2300258 (2023).
20. D. Ladika, A. Butkus, V. Melissinaki, *et al.*, “X-photon 3d lithography by fs-oscillators: wavelength-independent and photoinitiator-free,” *Light: Adv. Manufacturing* **5**, 567 (2025).
21. M. Marini, A. Nardini, R. Martínez Vázquez, *et al.*, “Microlenses fabricated by two-photon laser polymerization for cell imaging with non-linear excitation microscopy,” *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **33**(39), 2213926 (2023).
22. G. Zyla, G. Maconi, A. Nolvi, *et al.*, “3d micro-devices for enhancing the lateral resolution in optical microscopy,” *Light: Adv. Manufacturing* **5**, 204 (2024).
23. H. Wei, W. Hu, J. Hu, *et al.*, “3d printed near-infrared high-numerical aperture achromatic metalens,” *iScience* **28**(6), 112628 (2025).
24. P. Ruchka, S. Hammer, M. Rockenhäuser, *et al.*, “Microscopic 3d printed optical tweezers for atomic quantum technology,” *Quantum Sci. Technol.* **7**(4), 045011 (2022).
25. M. Sartison, K. Weber, S. Thiele, *et al.*, “3d printed micro-optics for quantum technology: Optimised coupling of single quantum dot emission into a single-mode fibre,” *Light: Advanced Manufacturing* **2**(2), 103 (2021).
26. L. Bremer, K. Weber, S. Fischbach, *et al.*, “Quantum dot single-photon emission coupled into single-mode fibers with 3d printed micro-objectives,” *APL Photonics* **5**(10), 106101 (2020).
27. M. Deubel, G. Von Freymann, M. Wegener, *et al.*, “Direct laser writing of three-dimensional photonic-crystal templates for telecommunications,” *Nat. Mater.* **3**(7), 444–447 (2004).
28. H. Toshiyoshi, “Mems for micro optics: from fiber optic communication to display (invited paper),” in *Optomechatronic Micro/Nano Devices and Components*, vol. 6050 Y. Katagiri, ed. (2005). p. 605007.
29. J. Müller, V. Kebbel, and W. Jüptner, “Digital holography as a tool for testing high-aperture micro-optics,” *Opt. Laser Eng.* **43**(7), 739–751 (2005).
30. H. Wang, Y. Liu, Q. Ruan, *et al.*, “Off-axis holography with uniform illumination via 3d printed diffractive optical elements,” *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **7**(12), 1900068 (2019).
31. S. Schmidt, S. Thiele, A. Toulouse, *et al.*, “Tailored micro-optical freeform holograms for integrated complex beam shaping,” *Optica* **7**(10), 1279 (2020).
32. P. Ruchka, A. Kushwaha, J. A. Marathe, *et al.*, “3d-printed micro-axicon enables extended depth-of-focus intravascular optical coherence tomography in vivo,” *Adv. Photonics* **7**(02), 026003 (2025).
33. A. M. Upadhyaya, M. K. Hasan, S. Abdel-Khalek, *et al.*, “A comprehensive review on the optical micro-electromechanical sensors for the biomedical application,” *Front. Public Health* **9**, 759032 (2021).
34. J. Jahns and S. Sinzinger, “Microoptics for biomedical applications,” *American Biotechnology Laboratory* **18** (2000).
35. F. Lux, A. Calikoglu, C. Klusmann, *et al.*, “3d nanoprinted catadioptric fiber sensor for dual-axis distance measurement during vitrectomy,” *Appl. Opt.* **63**(11), 2806 (2024).
36. S. You, J. Li, W. Zhu, *et al.*, “Nanoscale 3d printing of hydrogels for cellular tissue engineering,” *J. Mater. Chem. B* **6**(15), 2187–2197 (2018).
37. J. Li, S. Thiele, R. W. Kirk, *et al.*, “3d-printed micro lens-in-lens for in vivo multimodal microendoscopy,” *Small* **18**(17), 2107032 (2022).
38. S. M. Kavic and M. D. Basson, “Complications of endoscopy,” *Am. J. Surg.* **181**(4), 319–332 (2001).
39. A. Sergeev, V. Gelikonov, G. Gelikonov, *et al.*, “In vivo endoscopic oct imaging of precancer and cancer states of human mucosa,” *Opt. Express* **1**(13), 432 (1997).
40. J. Kim, J. Xing, H. S. Nam, *et al.*, “Endoscopic micro-optical coherence tomography with extended depth of focus using a binary phase spatial filter,” *Opt. Lett.* **42**(3), 379 (2017).
41. H. Pahlevaninezhad, M. Khorasaninejad, Y.-W. Huang, *et al.*, “Nano-optic endoscope for high-resolution optical coherence tomography in vivo,” *Nat. Photonics* **12**(9), 540–547 (2018).
42. J. Izatt, M. Kulkarni, H.-W. Wang, *et al.*, “Optical coherence tomography and microscopy in gastrointestinal tissues,” *IEEE J. Sel. Top. Quantum Electron.* **2**(4), 1017–1028 (1996).
43. D. Huang, E. A. Swanson, C. P. Lin, *et al.*, “Optical coherence tomography,” *Science* **254**(5035), 1178–1181 (1991).
44. L. Liu, J. A. Gardecki, S. K. Nadkarni, *et al.*, “Imaging the subcellular structure of human coronary atherosclerosis using micro-optical coherence tomography,” *Nat. Med.* **17**(8), 1010–1014 (2011).
45. A. Grushina, “Direct-write grayscale lithography,” *Adv. Opt. Technol.* **8**(3-4), 163–169 (2019).
46. L. Siegle, S. Ristok, and H. Giessen, “Complex aspherical singlet and doublet microoptics by grayscale 3d printing,” *Opt. Express* **31**(3), 4179 (2023).
47. L. Siegle, D. Xie, C. A. Richards, *et al.*, “Diffractive microoptics in porous silicon oxide by grayscale lithography,” *Opt. Express* **32**(20), 35678 (2024).